

**WYDZIAŁ PRAWA,
PRAWA KANONICZNEGO
I ADMINISTRACJI**

PATRONAT HONOROWY
WOJEWODA LUBELSKI
PRZEMYSŁAW CZARNEK

Wydział Prawa, Prawa Kanonicznego i Administracji
Katolicki Uniwersytet Lubelski Jana Pawła II
Polskie Towarzystwo Studiów Europejskich – Oddział Lubelski
Sekcja Prawa i Instytucji Europejskich
oraz
Zachodnie Centrum Naukowe Narodowej Akademii Nauk Prawnych Ukrainy
Katedra Europeistyki - Wydział Stosunków Międzynarodowych
Lwowskiego Uniwersytetu Narodowego im. Iwana Franki

zapraszają na
**międzynarodową konferencję inauguracyjną pracę
Sekcji Prawa i Instytucji Europejskich
Polskiego Towarzystwa Studiów Europejskich**

Przeobrażenia instytucjonalno-ustrojowe Unii Europejskiej oraz państw członkowskich

RAMOWY PROGRAM KONFERENCJI

20 września 2018 r. (czwartek)
godz. 16.00

Powitanie Uczestników i Gości konferencji –
dr hab. **Elżbieta Szczot**, prof. KUL – Prezes
Oddziału Lubelskiego Polskiego Towarzystwa
Studiów Europejskich, Koordynator SPIIE PTSE

OTWARCIE KONFERENCJI:

Prof. zw. dr hab. **Konstanty Adam Wojtaszczyk**,
Dyrektor Instytutu Europeistyki Uniwersytetu
Warszawskiego, Prezes Polskiego Towarzystwa
Studiów Europejskich
Ks. prof. dr hab. **Krzysztof Burczak** – Prodziekan
Wydziału Prawa, Prawa Kanonicznego
i Administracji KUL
Wystąpienie przedstawiciela Wojewody
Lubelskiego

PANEL I. PRZEOBRAŻENIA INSTYTUCJONALNE UNII EUROPEJSKIEJ

Moderator: dr hab. Piotr Tosiek, UMCS

Wystąpienie Pana Prof. UW **Piotra Wawrzyka**

– Wiceministra Spraw Zagranicznych RP
*Instytucje Unii Europejskiej – czy istnieje
potrzeba zmian?*

Dr Michał **Peno**, Uniwersytet Szczeciński –

Wspólnota ideałów a wspólnota prawna

Dr Edyta **Krzysztofik**, KUL – Ewolucja wymiaru
sprawiedliwości Unii Europejskiej

Dr Jacek **Jaśkiewicz**, Akademia im. Jakuba

z Paradyża w Gorzowie Wlkp. – *Kontrola
efektywności działania administracji a standardy
europejskie*

Dr Agnieszka **Parol**, KUL – *Subdelegacja*

*kompetencji wykonawczych w strukturze
instytucjonalnej Unii Europejskiej*

Dr Robert **Tabaszewski**, KUL – *Dopuszczalność*

*egzekwowania tzw. unijnej klauzuli
homogeniczności w świetle zasady suwerenności
państwa członkowskiego*

PANEL II. PRZEOBRAŻENIA USTROJOWE PAŃSTW W KONTEKŚCIE INTEGRACJI EUROPEJSKIEJ

Moderator: dr hab. Beata Piskorska, KUL
sala – CI-205

Dr hab. Viktoriya **Serzhanova**, Uniwersytet
Rzeszowski – *Europeizacja konstytucji narodowych
w wyniku oddziaływania procesów integracji
regionalnej*

Prof. dr Mustafa **Yasan**, Sakarya University –
*Institutional Transformation of Turkish Commercial
Law as a Result of the European Union Candidacy*

Prof. zw. Miomira **Kostić**, dr Aleksandar **Mihajlović**,
Wydział Prawa, Uniwersytet w Niszu, Serbia – *The
significance of illiteracy: The past or still the present
phenomenon*

Prof. Darko **Dimovski**, Wydział Prawa, Uniwersytet
w Niszu, Serbia, Ivan **Milić**, Wydział Prawa,
Uniwersytet w Nowym Sadzie, Serbia – *Analysis of
the law on the prevention of domestic violence.*

Dr hab. Marzena **Dyjakowska**, prof. KUL – *Wpływ
odwoływania się władz komunistycznych w Polsce
w latach 1944-1947 do Konstytucji marcowej na
kształtowanie ustroju*

PANEL III. INICJATYWY REGIONALNE W UNII EUROPEJSKIEJ I W PAŃSTWACH STOWARZYSZONYCH

Moderator: dr Jacek Szczot
sala CI-201

Dr Jacek **Szczot** – Wyższa Szkoła Kadr
Menedżerskich w Koninie – *Współpraca państw
w ramach Partnerstwa Wschodniego*

Arkadiusz **Urban** – Doradca Sekretarza Stanu
w Gabinetnie Prezesa Rady Ministrów, Warszawa –
Międzymorze – od idei do realizacji

Katarzyna **Woch**, KUL – *Wpływ środków
europejskich na rozwój współpracy pomiędzy Polską
a Ukrainą.*

Zakończenie obrad pierwszego dnia konferencji

godz. 19.00 Kolacja

LWÓW

21 września 2018 r. (piątek)
godz. 17.00

Kuria Metropolitalna, ul. Winniczenka 32
Wystąpienie Abp. **Mieczysława Mokrzyckiego**,
Metropolity Lwowskiego,
Rola Kościoła w integracji europejskiej

22 września 2018 r. (sobota)
godz. 11.00, sala 205

Lwowski Uniwersytet Narodowy im. Iwana Franki

WYSTĄPIENIA:

Prof. dr hab. Michał **Mikiewich** – Prodziekan
Wydziału Stosunków Międzynarodowych,
Kierownik Katedry Europeistyki Lwowskiego
Uniwersytetu Narodowego im. Iwana Franki –
*„Інституційно-правовий механізм співпраці
між Україною та ЄС в умовах асоціації”
(Instytucjonalny i prawny mechanizm współpracy
Ukrainy i UE w umowach stowarzyszeniowych)*
Prof. dr hab. Viktor **Hryshchuk** – Dyrektor
Zachodniego Centrum Naukowego Narodowej
Akademii Nauk Prawnych Ukrainy, *Kwestia
reformowania ukraińskiego systemu państwa
i prawa w drodze ku integracji europejskiej.*

KATOLICKI
UNIwersytet
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JANA PAWŁA II

KUL
1918

20-22
w r z e ś n i a
2018

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Dr hab. Elżbieta Szczot, prof. KUL,

– przewodnicząca

Dr hab. Piotr Tosiek, UMCS

Prof. zw. dr hab. Janusz Węc, UJ

Prof. dr Mustafa Yasan, SAU

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– przewodnicząca

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Dr Jacek Szczot

PARTNER ORGANIZACYJNY:

Fundacja Wschodnioeuropejski

Instytut Nauki i Rozwoju

Instytut „Międzymorze”

Katolicki Uniwersytet Lubelski Jana Pawła II

20 września 2018 r.,

godz. 16.00-20.00

Collegium Iuridicum

Lublin, ul. Spokojna 1, sala 204

Lwowski Uniwersytet Narodowy im. Iwana Franki

22 września 2018 r.,

godz. 11.00, Lwów,

ul. Strzelców Siczowych 19,

sala 205

Faculty of Law, Canon Law and Administration
John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin

Polish Society for European Studies - Lublin
Section of Law and EU Institutions

invite you to the
international seminar inaugurating the work of Law and EU Institutions Section
Polish Society for European Studies

Institutional and political transformations of the European Union and Member States
20 - 23 September 2018

John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin
September 20, 2018 16.00-19.00
Collegium Iuridicum
Lublin, st. Spokojna 1, CI-204

Lviv
21 - 23 September 2018
Framework conference program
September 20, 2018
Time: 4:00 pm

Welcoming participants and guests of the seminar - dr hab. Elżbieta Szczot, prof. KUL - President of the Lublin Branch of the Polish Society for European Studies, Coordinator SPiE PTSE

Opening of the seminar - Prof. zw. dr hab. Konstanty Adam Wojtaszczyk, President of the Polish Society for European Studies

Panel I. Institutional transformations of the European Union

Moderator: dr hab. Piotr Tosiek, UMCS

Speech by Prof. UW of Piotr Wawrzyk - Deputy Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Poland

Panelists:

... ..

**Panel II. Systemic transformations of states in the context
European integration**

Moderator: dr hab. Beata Piskorska, KUL

Panelists:

... ..

Discussion

Conclusions

The end of the first day of the seminar

7:00 -20:00 pm Dinner

Scientific Committee

Professor zw. dr hab. Konstanty A. Wojtaszczyk, University of Warsaw

Professor zw. dr hab. Wiesław Bokajło, WSB Wr

Professor zw. Zbigniew Czachór, AMU

Professor dr hab. Dariusz Niedźwiecki, UJ

Dr hab. Krzysztof Orzeszyna, prof. KUL

Dr hab. Beata Piskorska, KUL

Dr hab. Viktoria Serzhanova, UR,

Dr hab. Wojciech Szczepan Staszewski, prof. KUL

Dr hab. Elżbieta Szczot, prof. KUL

Dr hab. Ewa Tuora-Schwierskott

Professor zw. dr hab. Janusz Węc, UJ

SCIENTIFIC AND INTEGRATION TRIP TO LVIV

21-22-23 SEPTEMBER 2018

Framework program

September 21st (Friday) 8:15 am departure by coach from the Castle Square in Lublin

Route Lublin-Lviv - 220 km

Planned arrival to Lviv around 2 pm Ukrainian time.

Accommodation

Lunch 2-3 pm

5 pm Meeting with Archbishop Mieczysław Mokrzycki, Metropolitan of Lviv. Visiting the Archdiocesan Museum

Visiting Lviv

Dinner

September 22nd (Saturday)

10:00 am meeting at the University of Ivan Franko in Lviv

Lunch 1-2 pm

Visiting the Old Town

Departure to the Łyczakowski cemetery

Dinner

September 23rd (Sunday)

Lunch

around 2-3 pm departure to Poland

on the way back visiting Żółkiew

Cost of the trip - 700 PLN – includes:

conferences in Lublin and in Lviv

→ 2 nights accomodation

→ alimentation

→ transfer by coach

→ insurance

Payments to the account below shall be made until **September 5th** this year, with a note:

Lublin-Lviv Conference

Name: Fundacja Wschodnioeuropejski Instytut Nauki i Rozwoju

Address: Królewska 3, 20-109 Lublin

account number: 69 2030 0045 1110 0000 0285 3670

KRS: 0000557336

NIP: 9462652859

REGON: 361509907

The Foundation issues a confirmation / invoice for the conference fee. In order to receive an invoice, please provide the required data:

- name of the entity (full name of the university)
- address
- NIP

For insurance of the participants of the conference and to prepare a list of participants

- to the border - it is required to provide:
- First name and last name
- PESEL
- Passport number

These information should be sent to: eszczot@kul.pl

Participants are asked to check the validity of their passports and take it with them.

The deadline for submitting participation by **13 August this year.**

Payments until September 5.

E-mail contact:

eszczot@kul.pl

Miomira Kostić, LL.D.

Full Professor,

Faculty of Law, University of Niš

Aleksandar Mihajlović, PhD student

Faculty of Law, University of Niš

**THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ILLITERACY:
The past or contemporary phenomenon¹**

Abstract: In the paper, the authors highlighted the notion of literacy / illiteracy. Literacy is the ability to use the available system of symbols, which are at the heart of learning and teaching, for the purpose of understanding and compiling, or for the purpose of making communication sense and knowledge. Literacy is a wider concept of a printed word that is read or written. It is shaped by context, participants, and applied technologies. Today's context includes the development of technologies, along with visual, audio, gesture, space, or multimedia discourse. Some scholars claim that there was always a crisis moment in relation to literacy, historically observed. Taking into account tradition, criticism and approaches in relation to literacy, UNESCO documents have separated four areas of literacy understanding: literacy as an independent set of skills; Literacy as something that is being applied, practiced and established; Literacy as a learning process; literacy as text, content of words. Criminological literature does not have a single understanding of how education can affect the manifestation of delinquency activities (pessimistic and optimistic currents), although statistical data show that among the delinquents there are a large number of those with low education and a lower degree of culture.

Keywords: literacy; illiteracy; culture; delinquency; UNESCO.

Introduction

¹ On August 2, 2018, Prof. Dr. Miomira Kostic received a letter of invitation from Dr hab. Elżbieta Szczot, prof. KUL President of the PTSE Lublin Branch for the participation at the Conference: Section of Law and European Institutions at the Polish Association for European Studies, which was planned to be hold September 20-23, 2018, Lublin, at the John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin, as well as in Lviv Ukraine, under the title "Institutional and political transformations of the European Union and the Member States".

Being literate means the personality of a person who can read and write, who is literate. Literacy also includes knowledge of the system of writing and reading, as well as the correct grammatical and stylistic writing skills.² Therefore, at first glance, literacy should be a word that everyone understands well. But at the same time, literacy is, conceptually, the term that carries complexity and dynamism in itself, and which is constantly explained and determined in many ways. The perceptions, widely circulated to the public, on what are the notions of literacy or illiteracy, are constantly influenced by: academic research, work programs of various institutions, national determinations, cultural values, as well as personal experiences.

In the academic community, literacy theories developed, starting with those who have in the center of interest changes in a person to an individual, to those who represent a much more complex view and which includes a much wider social context, as a "literate environment", or "literally society ". This, however, influences the support and enabling of the literacy practices of the population. As a result of the development of these perceptions and advances in relation to literacy, as well as the understanding of the international political community, there have been some visible shifts. First, from the understanding of literacy, as a simple process for achieving basic cognitive skills, to the use of these skills in ways that contribute to socio-economic development, all the way to expanding the capacity of social consciousness and critical reflection as a basis for personal and social change.

What is available on the Internet, as an open library, can certainly be sublimated through literacy definitions, such as: the quality or level of someone's literacy, the quality of reading or writing; or, having the education: "to examine someone's education"; or, knowledge of a particular subject or field of science: "improving someone's knowledge of finance."³

Apparently simply, these definitions can also be shown in their complexity. Hence, literacy is the ability to use the available system of symbols, which are the basis of learning and teaching, for the purpose of understanding and compiling, or for the purpose of making communication sense and knowledge. Literacy is a wider concept of a printed word that is read or written. It is shaped by context, participants, and applied technologies. Today's context includes the development of technologies, along with visual, audio, gesture, space, or multimedia discourse.⁴

² *Dictionary of the Serbian language. (2007). Novi Sad: Matica srpska, p. 930.*

³ *Dictionary.com, <http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/literacy>, Retrieved: 11. 3. 2015.*

⁴ *Reflections about the Meaning of Literacy, April 27, 2012, <http://www.literacyinlearningexchange.org/defining-literacy>, access: 11. 3. 2015.*

Being literate is the heart of learning in any subject area. In fact, being literate is a prerequisite for learning. In the way that students progress during their education and approaching in certain areas more and more, the concept of literacy becomes more and more challenging. Students use different sources of knowledge, with increasingly complex use of languages and structures, with particularly sophisticated graphic and numerical presentations. They learn writing and reading strategies, use different records and suitable data sources, in each area.

In addition, literacy has always included a collection of cultural and communication practices, which is shared among members of a particular group. How does one society and technology, and literacy change? A man of the 21st century must have a wide range of abilities and skills, numerous forms of literacy. This literacy, like reading the press on-line or participating in virtual classrooms, is a multiplicative, dynamic, flexible skill. Similar to the past, forms of literacy are inseparably linked to historical circumstances, life opportunities, and social paths of individuals and groups.

Finally, literacy implies a continuity of learning, enabling an individual to achieve his goals, to develop his potentials and knowledge, and to participate fully in his community and wider social environment.⁵

Historical review of literacy and literacy

Some scientists, who for decades have dealt with the phenomenon of literacy, such as Graff, (Graff, 1994), argue that literally there has always been a crisis moment, historically observed. Schools and universities have consistently represented easily attractive targets, with established responsibility and guilt, in difficult, humorous times, as well as the issue of literacy of the population. In addition to existing contradictions, literacy levels of the population spontaneously serve as symbols and symptoms, causes and consequences. They, in themselves, are suitable, simple symbols for mass critique, which is not directed to essential sources, or even in the ultimate, successful transformation of the issue. That's why this author quotes the words of

⁵ *Reflections about the Meaning of Literacy*, April 27, 2012, <http://www.literacyinlearningexchange.org/defining-literacy>, access: 11. 3. 2015.

historian Michael Katz that nearly forty years ago education was proposed as a means to solve every major social problem.⁶

Graff even distinguishes several key points that relate to the literacy history. Namely, this author points out that literacy, as well as education and learning, has its own historical foundations and foundations. Likewise, these processes are strongly resistant to change. Their basics are "fundamentally complex," practical and theoretical. Literacy places itself in a hierarchical relationship of power and wealth, as opposed to egalitarian democracy. Then, as its contribution to the development of the economy, politics, society. Even elementary literacy, as well as learning and practice, represent a psychic, neurological, and cognitive action. Learning literacy is a complex task. Therefore, the different social circumstances, the importance of the media, the technology, the pedagogy, and the institutional settings do not imply the motivation of the individual by itself-the perception of needs, sometimes defensive, or filled with fear, sometimes with great satisfaction and satisfaction, is undoubtedly a greater incentive than that biological age and social status.

The great dream of the reformers was to create formal, compulsory, mass public schools "like the expected side for the virtual universal transmission of a minimum level of literacy, reciprocally distributed with the basic dogmas of secular morality."⁷

Literacy is a part of elementary education. However, the main difficulties are the prevalence of recording unequal opportunities and schooling, from radically different bases for children from unequal social classes, races, and ethical groups, and professor's expectations, in connection with the obedience of different young people. Gender access is also significant. Motivation among young people varies widely, in different social lines, but also between children and young people of the same origin.

Similar to the fact that individuals follow different paths towards literacy and learning, historically, and human societies have taken different paths in attaining higher levels of popular literacy.⁸

⁶Harvey J. Graff. „Literacy, myths, and legacies: lessons from the history of literacy. U: *Functional Literacy: theoretical issues and educational implications*. (Ed. by Ludo Verhoeven). (1994). Nethralands: John Benjamins Publishing. p. 38.

https://books.google.rs/books?hl=sr&lr=&id=z7nbgVnZyYMC&oi=fnd&pg=PA37&dq=history+of+literacy&ots=KMw46lcL6&sig=laSLEIovvw36eMUh3FgVhprYw_s&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=history%20of%20literacy&f=false, access: 11. 3. 2015.

⁷ Harvey J. Graff, op. cit., p. 50.

⁸ Harvey J. Graff, op. cit., pp. 43-52.

For example, in the United States, there is a long tradition in the state's efforts to literate the population, even longer than two hundred years. From the earliest days of the founding of a federal state, governments have always provided funds to justify, encourage and expand programs to help adults overcome educational difficulties that prevent successful and responsible participation in the life and progress of one nation. Therefore, at the federal level, the United States organized evening schools for adults, education through courses, and education for naturalized Americans. Records in state archives contain evidence of organized education for adults, dating back to the 18th century. Until the early 1960s, the poverty and literacy of adults became the subject of attention again in the United States. In 1964, the Economic Opportunity Act was adopted, which in its head stipulates the normative basis of the basic adult education program as a special budget line. In the first year, after the law was passed, the United States allocated \$ 18.6 million for various adult education programs.⁹

In Europe, EU education ministers have set a common goal to reduce the rate of fifteen-year-olds who have not mastered reading basics from the current 20% to 15% by 2020. According to the PISA Report of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), in 2009, 41% of pupils in Bulgaria did not reach an adequate level of functional literacy, and in Romania 40.4%. Still, the number of functionally illiterate people decreased by 10.1 percentage points in Bulgaria in 2006 and 13.1 percentage points in Romania. In 2009, the smallest functionally illiterate pupils in the EU recorded in Finland 8.1%.

According to PISA report for 2009, the percentage of students in Serbia who did not reach the level of functional literacy decreased from 52% in 2006 to 33% in 2009. According to students' reading literacy, Serbia was ahead of Bulgaria, Romania, Montenegro and Albania, and lagged behind Slovenia and Croatia. The report showed that there is a significant gap between the sexes in the EU, as boys (26.6%) who are not literate enough are significantly higher than girls (13.3%). Among the sexes, the lowest is expressed in the Netherlands, where, according to data from 2009, 10.8% of girls and 17.9% of boys did not master enough reading and writing. Denmark followed (11.5% of girls and 19% of boys) and Belgium (13.8% girls and 21.5% boys). This gap is most pronounced in Malta, where 48.4% of boys did not master enough writing and

⁹ *History of the Adult Education Act*, <http://www.naepdc.org/issues/AEAHistort.htm>, access: 18. 3. 2015.

reading, while the girl was 24.4%, followed by Bulgaria (52% boys and 29.2% girls) and Lithuania (35.5 % of boys and 13% of girls).¹⁰

In countries where illiteracy is eradicated, the issue of literacy is not included in the census. In our country it is regularly monitored on all previous lists, and it is set up for all persons older than ten years. According to the 2002 census, there were 232,925 illiterates in Serbia, which was 3.5% of the total population over ten years old. Of the number of illiterates, 81.1% were in central Serbia, or 188.835 persons, and in Vojvodina 44.090, or 18.9%. At the same time, the share of illiterates in the total population over ten years was 3.8% in central Serbia, and 2.4% in Vojvodina.¹¹ The results of the 2012 census showed that the number of illiterate people in Serbia has been halved compared to the 2002 census, and now there are about 165,000, of which more than 80% are women. Incomplete primary school has about 677,000 inhabitants of Serbia or 11%, and in 2002 there were more than one million. With higher education in Serbia, there are slightly more than 650,000 inhabitants, which is almost 11%, as opposed to 2002, when it was 6.52%. Computer is illiterate more than 50% of the population of Serbia.¹²

Areas of understanding the character of literacy

Since the mid-20th century, scientists have begun to devote special attention to defining literacy, and their work has had direct implications in the approaches to the practice and policy of individual countries. Scientists from a wide range of interests, in the fields of psychology, economics, linguistics, sociology, anthropology, philosophy and history, have begun to participate in a debate of the diverse context of what is literacy and how it is broadly related to education and learning. Taking into account tradition, criticism and approaches to literacy, UNESCO documents have separated four areas of literacy comprehension. These are: literacy as an independent set of skills; Literacy as something that is being applied, practiced and established; Literacy as a learning process; literacy as text, content of words.¹³

¹⁰ „Insufficient literacy problem in both the EU and Serbia“, 7. 9. 2012.

<http://www.euractiv.rs/srbija-i-eu/4670-nedovoljna-pismenost-problem-i-u-eu-i-srbiji>, access: 24. 3. 2015.

¹¹ „Image of illiteracy in Serbia“, Belgrade: Demographic Review, Vol. IV, no. 16/2003, p. 1.

<http://www.minrzs.gov.rs/files/doc/podrobnosti/Demografski%20pregled/2003/16%20Slika%20nepismenosti%20u%20Srbiji.pdf> access: 24. 3. 2015.

¹² „165,000 people in Serbia are illiterate“, <http://www.dnevnik.rs/drustvo/u-srbiji-165000-nepismenih>, access: 24. 3. 2015.

¹³ Understandings of literacy, p. 148. http://www.unesco.org/education/GMR2006/full/chapt6_eng.pdf

Literacy as a stand alone skill set includes reading, writing, and speaking skills. The most common understanding of literacy is precisely that it is a set of assessable skills, especially cognitive skills of reading and writing, which are independent of the context in which they have been acquired since that person's past life. This understanding of literacy also includes computing, as well as the ability to access knowledge and information.

The next field of understanding of literacy refers to how literacy is applied, practiced and established, and more is a way of drawing attention to literacy as a skill applied in the right way. In the sixties and seventies of the 20th century, with this understanding, the importance of literacy on socio-economic development was initially emphasized.

Literacy as a learning process implies that when one learns, it becomes literate. It is one of the andragogical principles, or the theory of adult education, according to which the student is at the center of the educational process, with the critical reflection of that center.

Literacy as text, content composed of words is the fourth way of understanding literacy, as the subject matter, in which the nature of that text is compiled and used by a written individual. The texts vary, depending on the subject and genre. This method involves an analysis of content, similar to a socio-linguistic discourse.¹⁴

Explanations of literacy inevitably lead to the explanation of the opposite phenomenon - illiteracy. One of the archeologists of philosophical thought of the 20th century A.N. Alfred North Whitehead said: "Not ignorance, but the ignorance of ignorance is the death of knowledge." Different notions are indicated in science, such as illiteracy, semi-epidemic, functional illiteracy, followed by frustrations, anxiety and disappointment of a person with a lack of literacy. In addition, there is a reference to hidden illiteracy, which means ignoring, or ignoring your own ignorance. Illiterate people hide their illiteracy from themselves, and often do not fully understand the information and ideas they receive from the outside world. And since illiteracy has never been identified as such by an illiterate person itself, it is hidden from others.¹⁵

The consequences of illiteracy

access: 10. 3. 2015.

¹⁴ Understandings of literacy, op.cit., p. 149-152.

¹⁵ *Applied Scholastics*, <http://www.appliedscholastics.org/education-issues/hidden-illiteracy-the-ignorance-of-ignorance.html>, access: 10. 3. 2015.

Illiteracy can affect both the individual and the society as a whole. This relates to the following aspects of life: the limitation of the ability to receive and understand complementary information; unemployment (the unemployment rate is 2-4 times higher for those with lower education levels than for those with higher education); lower salary; doing simpler jobs; limitation of lifelong learning opportunities and professional development; an uncertain financial situation; adding little importance to reading and education in the family, which often leads to the intergenerational transmission of illiteracy; low self-esteem, which can lead to isolation; health effects (illiterate people experience injuries at work, they need a longer recovery and more frequent abuse of medicines, due to ignorance about how to protect their health and because they have difficulties reading and understanding relevant information such as warnings, dosing, contra-indications) .

Illiteracy has its consequences for society. Since literacy is an essential means for an individual and society to be competitive in the conditions of a new global economy, many positions remain unfilled due to the lack of personal ability to reach them. Difficulties in understanding social resources reduce the level of community involvement and participation in a civil society.¹⁶

Criminological literature does not have a single understanding of how education can affect the manifestation of delinquency activities (pessimistic and optimistic currents),¹⁷ although statistical data show that among the delinquents there are a large number of those with low education and a lower degree of culture.¹⁸ Among many factors related to the school's impact on crime, the failure of school, school drop-out and low level of education are particularly high. Poor success in learning, repetition of grades, poor progress in learning school materials affect the inability to acquire the necessary knowledge and education, the lack of working habits, and the appearance of certain behavioral disorders, such as: schooling, sketches, alcoholism, drug addiction , prostitution, committing criminal offenses.¹⁹

¹⁶ *Consequences of illiteracy*, <https://www.fondationalphabetisation.org/en/foundation/causes-of-illiteracy/consequences-of-illiteracy/> access: 10. 3. 2015.

¹⁷ Lombrozo pointed out that children who already show a stigmatized criminal in elementary school should be separated and subjected to special treatment, designed to strengthen inhibitory factors and suppress criminal instances. Mannheim, H., *Comparative Criminology*, London, Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1970, Vo. 1, p. 224.

¹⁸ Milutinović, M., *Criminology*, Belgrade, Faculty of Administration, 1988, pp. 323-324.

¹⁹ Konstantinović-Vilić, S., Nikolić-Ristanović, V., *Criminology*, Student Cultural Center Niš, Niš, 1998. p. 315.

The drop-out factor is considered to be the main cause of delinquency and the emergence of drug addiction among children. The results of the research are sometimes contradictory, especially when it is found that many deviant behaviors are done by those who attend school, but it is, again, easier to discover or arrest those who have left school. Likewise, it is more likely that delinquent behavior, especially what is done with a peer group, will make it easier to make a decision to leave the school.²⁰ The school environment, as well as the difficulty of fitting into newly formed relationships, requires the ability to adapt, which has an almost decisive contribution to the child's further attitude towards school and education, and the possible occurrence of deviant and delinquent behavior, even more than the contribution of intellectual abilities.

However, the processes of education and training, although they contain a number of shortcomings of technical and substantive nature can not have direct effect criminogenic factors. When a child comes from a degraded family, the school can hardly affect the child in the opposite direction from that in the family, which is primary, because the new environment, with special demands and a specific authoritative relationship, only burdens and confuses an already victimized child. Parents themselves will become discouraged in conditions of social isolation, poverty, marital separation or lack of social support, and as a consequence of their demoralization, they will be less able to establish contact with children of lower intellectual abilities and to support them in developing emotional control, learning and other social skills. All of these disadvantages influence the child to be poorly prepared for the social and educational requirements set by the school. Also, a child entering school with developed abilities to exhibit aggressiveness and feeling unfulfilled is poorly prepared to master reading, which is the most important educational task of the first years of school.

In addition, another feature, in many high-risk factors of reporting violence and antisocial behavior in children, is the lack of family support to achieve good governance in school and advocacy to overcome school materials. Children from such families are closer to children of similar attitudes and behaviors, which creates great difficulties for teachers who unconsciously become inconsistent in their attitude towards pupils, verbally abuse them and create a forced relationship with children. Therefore, some sociologists point out that the "irony of life

²⁰ Clinard states the classification of ways to leave further education, such as: involuntary abandonment, abandonment due to mental retardation and school leaving by intellectually capable children. Clinard, B. M., *Sociology of deviant behavior*, New York, Holt, Rinehart and Winston, Inc. 1968. p. 715.

experience" violent patterns of teacher behavior revive the family experience of high-risk children and increase their problematic behavior. Thus, between aggressive, defenseless children and teachers, a gap is created that prevents the provision of support to problematic children. This can particularly be reflected in contacts between parents and teachers, in which the parent feels humiliation and pain due to the child's behavior.²¹

Those children who exhibit early and continuous antisocial behavior are more likely to show failure in learning in elementary school and lack of attachment to school. The early manifestation of continuous antisocial behavior in the early years of the primary school predicts that criminal and violent behavior will occur later. Children who exhibit antisocial behavior, such as aggression, negativistic mood and anger outbursts, during primary school age, are more likely to engage in crime and violence as adolescents and adults than children who do not exhibit antisocial behavior. Failure in learning is a risk factor of violence and delinquency, which is an indicator in the later years of elementary schooling, while the lack of attachment to the school leads to greater inclination towards delinquency than to young people who accept their position and role of pupils as something that is desired and leads to training for life.

A few final considerations

Communication among the members of the group does not represent a specific specificity of the human race, but members of other higher and lower animal species have their own particular communication. However, finding the letter is nevertheless an incomparably more important means of communication than any other "material aid through which messages arrive from their source (provider) to those to whom they are intended (recipients)". As Zvonarević observes, finding the letter has enabled messages among people to be sent and received, regardless of the one who sent them or created them. Because the scope of the message no longer depended on the strength of a person's voice, or the sound of drum beats.²²

The way, means, and goals achieved by exchanging messages among people is conditioned by the numerous exogenous and endogenous characteristics, and in particular the ultimate

²¹ Coie, J., *Prevention of Violence and Antisocial Behavior*, in: *Preventing Childhood Disorders, Substance Abuse and Delinquency*, (ed. Ray DeV Peters, Robert J. McMahon), SAGE Publications, Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi, 1996., p. 7-9.

²² Zvonarević, M. *Social psychology*. Zagreb, School book, 1976, p. 379.

invisible, or near, visible goals that are intended to be achieved. Nor is any effect of a message being acceptable to society at a given moment, nor is it always unacceptable. The end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st century brought a new, accelerated form of communication, through a special technical means, computers, and the virtual world, the Internet. Technical literacy has triggered many of the world's revolutions at the turn of the 21st century, on the one hand, while many individual aspirations, aspirations, events, in individual human lives have brought unprecedented challenges.

The issue of literacy and literacy of the population is not an individual, no regulated process, which should depend on the will of individuals. This is a state issue, as a priority, in order to achieve the national interest of the people, and therefore it must function with certain budgetary standards, envisaged not only for achieving the ultimate goal - basic literacy of the population, but for creating a highly sophisticated network of experts and institutions, did it. The eradication of illiteracy in our country must be a priority task for all educated people. The need for school and acquiring knowledge should return us in the time of Dositej Obradovic, whose "Life and Connected" continues to tell us about the urgent need of people for knowledge.